

Label Bas Carbone: a national forest carbon offsetting framework

Introduction

Carbon sequestration is an ecosystem service that forests and foresters provide to society. This action focuses on assessing the forest carbon balance of the Fumel area.

Methodology and results

A study on the wood resource was conducted in 2014 on the territory of the community of municipalities of Fumel Vallée du Lot and Montflanquinois. Having such data for this territory is valuable: these measurements were re-mobilized in the framework of the SPNA project to derive information on the "carbon balance" of local forests. The calculations show carbon stocks of 931 ± 120 thousand tons of carbon in the biomass and 672 thousand tons of carbon in the soil and litter. The flux study shows that the territory's forests are still a net carbon sink, although the dieback of chestnut coppice is a concern and could turn local forests into carbon sources.

The LBC is a French standard for carbon offsetting projects. It is used to label the contribution of companies and communities to CO₂ sequestration projects in the forest.

Currently there are 3 validated methods for labeling forest carbon offset projects:

- Afforestation of agricultural land or bushy wastelands;
- Reconstitution of degraded forests (storm, fire, intense dieback);
- Conversion of good thickets into high forests on stumps.

The community Fumel Vallée du Lot also sees it as an opportunity to promote the renewal of dying chestnut trees, as the forest is an important local resource for many businesses.

Figure 1. Label Bas Carbone post fire planting. Bernard Petit © CNPF

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/sylviculture-de-pr%C3%A9cision-en-nouvelle-aquitaine.html>

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